

The reptiles of Türkiye: An etymology

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Abstract

Here, we present the etymology of the Latin binomials of all reptile genera and species in Türkiye. According to our results, the names are mostly given according to the characteristics of the species or in honor of a person. Reviewing the etymologies of the Latin names of reptile species living in Türkiye, and compiling information and heritage will be very useful, especially for Turkish herpetology.

Keywords: Derivatio nominis, etymology, nomenclature, Reptilia, Turkish herpetofauna

Introduction

The system of binomial nomenclature was formally introduced by the “father of modern taxonomy” Carl Linnaeus, beginning with his work *Species Plantarum* in 1753. He wasn’t the first to attempt to standardize the names of plants and animals. Caspar Bauhin (1622) introduced in his book *Pinax theatrae botanici* many names of genera more than a century prior to Linnaeus (Hansen & Fox Maule, 1973). Now, the application of binomial nomenclature is managed by various internationally agreed codes of rules, of which the most important are the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN, 1999; “the Code” below). The origin of an internationally accepted Code is a result of the name confusion that arose in the zoological literature in the early 19th century. Following the publication of the 10th edition of the *Systema Naturae* by Linnaeus in

1758 and his adoption of binomial names for animal species in it, the new system expanded and developed in different ways in different places and for different animal groups in the next century (ICZN 2022). Taxonomists should pay more attention and care to the issues of etymology, aspect, and length of nomina for proper communication with all other biologists and non-biologists (Dubois, 2010a,b). Latin and Greek words commonly used in scientific names is intended to help those unfamiliar with classical languages understand and remember the names of organisms. The etymology of the terms in scientific names is often even more descriptive than the common names. Unfortunately, the information about the etymology of the scientific names is sometimes difficult to reach the original sources to confirm. A compiled etymology list for any taxa makes it easier for scientists to study the taxa and for people interested in the subject to access the information. Türkiye (Turkey) is the intersection of the Caucasus, the Irano-Anatolian, and Mediterranean hotspots (Mittermeier et al., 2011) and home to a total of 142 reptile species (10 chelonians, including 1 alien species, 71 lizards, 3 amphisbaenians, and 57 snakes) (Karataş et al., 2021; Yaşar et al., 2021). The etymology of Turkish reptiles has not been completely presented in other published works that have dealt with one or another aspect of the derivation of reptile scientific names (Beolens et al., 2013). Türkiye has a very rich fauna and the description of new species and subspecies and even genera of herpetofauna are still possible (e.g. Karakasi et al., 2021; Kurnaz & Şahin 2021). We have attempted to ascertain, as much as possible, the construction of the Latin binomials of all Turkish reptile genera and species. We believe that a review of these names is instructive, not only in codifying many aspects of the biology of the reptiles, in presenting a historical overview of collectors and taxonomic work in Türkiye.

Material and methods

Taxa: The listing of Turkish reptiles was based primarily on Karataş et al. (2021), Yaşar *et al.* (2021), and recent descriptions (Arribas et al., 2022; Kurnaz et al., 2022). We also examined numerous published works in addition to those included in the original papers presenting each binomial, including Bodenheimer (1944), Mertens (1952), Başoğlu & Baran (1977, 1980), and Baran (1976).

Methods: Taxa are listed in systematic order following Karataş et al. (2021), and Yaşar et al. (2021). Orders, families, and subfamilies, if appropriate, are given. Genera and species are arranged alphabetically. The authority and date are given after each species' name. Whenever possible, derivations of names are given. Major sources used include Jaeger (1950) and Beolens

et al. (2013). Original literature also was consulted for explanations of names or for clues in the descriptions.

Four standard dictionary entries for Latin verbs are given in the patterns (respectively, present indicative (singular 1st person), present infinitive, perfect active and supine) and which conjugation. Adjectives, on the other hand, are given as masculine, feminine, neutral or nominative and genitive, with the standard abbreviation.

Abbreviations: L.: Latin (classic), LL.: Late Latin, ML.: Medieval Latin, NL.: New (Modern) Latin; Gr.: Ancient Greek; TR.: Turkish; f.: femininum (feminine), m.: masculinum (masculine); n.: neutrum (neuter); Acc.: accūsātīvus (accusative); genet.: genetīvus (genetive), Nom.: nōminātīvus (nominative); *Comp.*: comparativus (comparative); *Sup.*: superlativus (superlative); *adv.*: adverbium (adverb); *dim.*: diminutivus (diminutive); *pl.*: pluralis (plural); *Sg.*: singulum (singular); q.v.: quod vidē (which see); «: derived from the next; »: derived from the previous.

Results

The etymology of scientific names:

Class: Reptilia Laurenti, 1768

rēptilis, -e; pl. rēptilēs, -ia L. : creeping, crawling [« **rēp/ō, -ere, rēpsī, rēptum**: to creep, crawl (third conjugation, no passivum)+ **-ilis, -ile**: suffix, used to form an adjective noun of relation].

Order Testudines - Turtles

testūdō, -inis; pl. testūdinēs, -um f. L. : tortoise, turtle, tortoise-shell [« **testa, -ae f.**: an earthen pot, piece of burned clay, brick or tile, shell or covering].

Suborder Cryptodira

krýptós (κρυπτός) **m.** Gr.: concealed, hidden, secret + **deiré** (δειρή), *genet. deirês* (δειρήσ) **f.** = **déré** (δέρη), *genet. dérēs* (δέρησ) **f.** Gr.: neck, throat, collar.

Family Chelonidae (Sea Turtles)

chelōnia, -ae f. L. :« **khelōnē** (χελώνη), *genet. khelōnēs* (χελώνης) **f.** Gr.: turtle, tortoise [related to **chelys, -os f.** L. « **khélýs** (χέλῤῥ) Gr.: tortoise] + **-ia** NL.: forming plurals of nouns [cf. **khelōnía** (χελωνία) Gr.: tortoise-stone, a kind of precious stone] + **-idae** *pl.* L.: used to form names of families of animals in taxonomy [« **-ídēs** (-ίδης) Gr.: a patronymic suffix].

Caretta caretta (Linnaeus, 1758)

The genus name was tautonomically copied from the specific epithet, coined by Carl Linnaeus from **caret m.** (loggerhead turtle - *Caretta caretta* or hawksbill turtle - *Eretmochelys imbricata*) in French, originating from **carey m.** (hawksbill turtle) in Spanish.

***Chelonia mydas* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

chelōnia,-ae f. L. turtle [q.v. **Chelonidae**]

Midās,-ae m. Sg. L. :« **Mídās** (Μίδᾱς), *genet.* **Mídou** (Μίδου) **m.** Gr.: In Greek mythology, Midas, king of Phrygia who was gifted the ability to turn everything he touched to gold.

Family Dermochelyidae (Leatherback Turtles)

***Dermochelys coriacea* (Vandelli, 1761)**

dérma (δέρμα), *genet.* **dérmatos** (δέρματος) **n.** Gr.: skin, hide + **khélýs** (χέλῦς) or **khélys** (χέλῦς), *genet.* **khélyos** (χέλῦος) **f.** Gr.: tortoise,

coriáceus,-a,-um L. : leathery, coriaceous [« **corium,-iī** (or **-ī**) **n.** L.: skin, leather, hide, crust, coat, shell upper layer + **-áceus,-a,-um**: a suffix means resembling].

Family Emydidae (Pond Turtles/Box and Water Turtles)

***Emys orbicularis* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

emys, *genet.* **emydos** or **emydis f.** L. :« **emýs** (ἐμύς), *genet.* **emýdos** (ἐμύδος) **f.** Gr.: freshwater tortoise (*E. orbicularis*).

orbiculāris,-e L.: circular, orbicular [« **orbiculus,-ī m.** *dim.*: a small disk; a sheave, roller, pulley + **-āris (-ar)**: an adjectival suffix; « **orbis,-is m.**: a ring, disk, circle + **-culus,-a,-um**: diminutive suffix].

Family Geoemydidae (Asian River Turtles, Leaf and Roofed Turtles, Asian Box Turtles)

geō- (γεω-) [« **gê** (γη), *genet.* **gês** (γης) **f.**] Gr.: earth, land, soil, contry + **emys** L.: freshwater tortoise [q.v. *Emys orbicularis*] + **-idae pl.** L.: a suffix to form names of families of animals.

***Trachemys scripta* (Thunberg in Schoepff, 1792) [alien taxon]**

trachy- :« **trākhýs** (τρᾱχῦς) **m.**, **trākheîa** (τρᾱχεῖᾱ) **f.**, **trākhý** (τρᾱχῦ) **n.** Gr.: rough, jagged, shaggy, prickly, rugged, harsh + **emys** L.: freshwater tortoise [q.v. *Emys orbicularis*]

scrīptus,-a,-um L.: written, having been written.

***Mauremys caspica* (Gmelin, 1774)**

maurós (μαυρός) **m./f.**, **maurón** (μαυρόν) **n.** Gr.: dark, dusky, dim, faint, obscure, shadowy + **emys** L.: freshwater tortoise [q.v. *Emys orbicularis*].

caspicus,-a,-um L.: Caspian; « **Caspius,-a,-um** L. [« **Káspios** (Κάσπιος) Gr.]: the Caspian Sea, related to Caspia.

Mauremys rivulata (Valenciennes, 1833)

rīvulātus,-a,-um = **rīvulāris,-e** L.: that inhabits small brooks or rivulets [« **rīvus,-ī m.**: stream, a small stream; brook, rivulet].

Family Trionychidae (Softshell Turtles)

Trionyx triunguis (Forskål, 1775)

tri- [« **trēs, genet. tria**] L.: three + **ónýx** (ὄνυξ), **genet. ónýkhos** (ὄνυχος) **m.** Gr.: claw, nail, hoof, talon,

tri- L.: three + **unguis,-is m.** L. nail (of finger or toes), claw, hoof.

Rafetus euphraticus (Daudin, 1802)

rafetus: « a softshell turtle shot by the French naturalist Guillaume-Antoine Olivier, while boating on the Euphrates (1797), near Anah, he called "*Testudo rafcht*", hearing the Arabs call it rafcht. Although the meaning of this name in Arabic is not written in the book, some modern Arabic web pages refer to the local name of the turtle in dictionaries as الرفش (*al-rafš*), which means "shovel" (Wikipedia, 2022). The genus *Rafetus* was described by John Edward Gray (1864) and *euphraticus* by Daudin (1802).

euphraticus m.; euphratica f. L.: pertaining to the Euphrates [« **Euphrātēs,-is** (or **-ae**) **m.** *Sg.* L.; « **Euphrātēs** (Εὐφράτης) **m.** Gr.; « **u-f-r-a-tu-u** /hUfrātuš/ Old Persian; « **ÍDPurattu** Akkadian]: the Euphrates river.

Family Testudinidae (Tortoises)

Testudo graeca Linnaeus, 1758

testūdō,-inis f. L. : tortoise [q.v. **Order Testudines**]

graecus,-a,-um L.: Greek, Grecian, of or pertaining to the Greek people [« **Graikós** (Γραικός) **m.**, **Graiké** (Γραική) **f.**, **Graikón** (Γραικόν) **n.** Gr.: Greek].

Testudo hermanni Gmelin, 1789

hermanni : « **Johann Hermann** [1738-1800], French physician and naturalist. He became professor of medicine (1769), then professor of philosophy (1778) at the Strasbourg School of Public Health, and continued as head of chemistry, natural history, and materia medica (1784) after Jacob Reinbold Spielmann. He became professor of botany and materia medica at the New School of Medicine (1794). He was in charge of the Strasbourg botanical garden, as well as a

library of 18,000 volumes and hundreds of animal and plant collections (today in the Strasbourg zoological museum). This is the most famous of the taxa dedicated to his name.

Suborder Amphisbaenia Gray, 1844

Family Amphisbaenidae (Worm Lizards)

amphisbaena, -ae f. L.: « **amphísbaina** (ἀμφίσβαινα), *genet.* **amphisbaínēs** (ἀμφίσβαίνης) Gr.: a kind of mythological serpent, with a head on both ends of its body and can move backward or forwards, in Libyan deserts [« **amphís** (ἀμφίς): on both sides + **baínō** (βαίνω): to go] + **-idae pl.** L.: a suffix to form names of families of animals.

***Blanus strauchi* (Bedriaga, 1884)**

blanus : « **blános** (βλάνος) Gr.: blind,

strauchii: « **Alexander Strauch** [1832–1893], Russian naturalist, better known as herpetologist. In 1861 he was the curator of the zoological museum at the Imperial Academy of Sciences in St. Petersburg, and he was the director of the museum between 1879 and 1890. He is known for establishing a world-class herpetology centre in St. Petersburg. Some other taxa dedicated to his name are: *Ctenotus strauchii* (lizard), *Eremias strauchi* (lizard), *Gloydus strauchi* (snake), *Neurergus strauchii* (salamander), and *Phrynocephalus strauchi* (lizard).

***Blanus aporus* Werner, 1898**

a- (α-) Gr.: not, without + **porus**, -ī m. L. [« **póros** (πορός) m. Gr.]: passage, pore, opening (on the skin or body, etc.).

***Blanus alexandri* Sindaco, Kornilios, Sacchi & Lymberakis, 2014**

alexandri: « **A. Allan Alexander** [fl. 1962], U.S. herpetologist. He worked in the Department of Biology at the University of Buffalo (New York, United States). Dedication to performing the most valuable work on the *Blanus strauchi* complex and realizing that eastern populations can be distinguished from the Cilician taxon *aporus*.

Suborder Sauria Macartney, 1802

saur- : « **saûros** (σαῦρος) m. = **saúrā** (σαύρᾱ) f. Gr.: lizard, reptile + **-ia**: plural suffix

Family Agamidae

agama Surinamese Sranan Tongo language: lizard [cf. **agamus,-a,-um** L.: unmarried; « **ágamos** (ἄγαμος) Gr.: unmarried, single; « **a-** (ἀ-): non, not, un- + **gámos** (γάμος): marriage, wedding, wedlock, bride-lock, matrimony] + **-idae pl.** L.: a suffix to form names of families of animals.

***Paralaudakia caucasia* (Eichwald, 1831)**

para- NL.: beside, between, around, adjacent, near, opposite of, above, over, through, false, resembling [« **pará** (παρά) Gr.: beside; next to, near, from; against, contrary to] + **laudakia**: unknown name for the genus *Laudakia*,

caucasicus,-a,-um L.: Caucasian [« **Caucasus,-ī m.** Sg. L. « **Kaúkasos** (Καύκασος) **m.** Gr.: The Caucasus Mountains].

***Stellagama stellio* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

stēlla,-ae f. L. : star + **agama** Surinamese: lizard [q.v. **Agamidae**],

stēlliō,-ōnis f. L. : newt with star-like spots on its back, stellion some small lizard.

***Phrynocephalus horvathi* Méhely, 1894**

phrȳnos,-ī = phrȳnus,-ī m. L. :« **phrynē** (φρύνη) or **phrȳnos** (φρῦνος) Gr.: toad, a kind of venomous frog + **-cephalus,-a,-um** NL.: headed; « **kephalē** (κεφαλή), *genet.* **kephalēs** (κεφαλῆς) **f.** Gr.: head, the top-most part, the most important part [cf. head is the most important part chub (*Squalius cephalus*); « **cephalus,-ī m.** L. « **képhalos** (κέφαλος) Gr.: a species of mullet (*Mugil*)]

horvathi :« **Géza Horváth** [1847–1937], a Hungarian doctor and entomologist internationally recognized for his work on bugs (Hemiptera) and he published over 350 papers. He also contributed extensively to the study of Hungarian scale insect fauna. Between 1895 and 1923, he was director of Zoology Department, the Hungarian National Museum (Beolens et al., 2011). Lajos Méhely (1894) described the agamid taxon as *Phrynocephalus helioscopus* var. *horvathi* and with noted that “*Der Freundlichkeit des Herrn Dr. G. von Horváth verdanke ich eine kleine Collection Batrachier und Reptilien aus Transkaukasien, die er im Monate Juni 1893 theils in der Gegend von Tiflis, Eriwan und Kvirili, theils in Aralich, am Fusse des Ararat gesammelt hat* (I owe a small collection of batrachians and reptiles from Transcaucasia to the friendliness of Dr. G. von Horváth, which he collected in June 1893, partly in the area of Tbilisi, Yerevan and Kvirili, also in Aralık, at the foot of Mount Ağrı). The specific name, *horvathi* must be in honor of Hungarian entomologist Géza Horváth. Another species of lizard, *Iberolacerta horvathi*, is named in his honor.

***Trapelus ruderatus* (Olivier, 1804)**

trapel-:« **trapelós** (τραπέλος) Gr.: one that turns easily,

rūderātus,-a,-um L.: covered with rubble, ager, full of rubble, lean, dry [« **rūdus,-eris n.** L.: lump (especially of copper or bronze), tile (on roof), debris, rubble].

Family Chamaeleonidae (Chameleons)

***Chamaeleo chamaeleon* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

chamaeleōn,-ōnis (or **-ōntis**) **m.** L. : chameleon (a kind of lizard); a plant with changeable leaves in colour; but literally “lion of the ground” [« **khamailéōn** (χαμαιλέων), *genet.* **khamailéontos** (χαμαιλέοντος) **m.** Gr.: chameleon (lizard), a kind of plant; « **khamai** (χαμαί) adv. Gr.: on the earth (ground) + **léōn** (λέων), *genet.* **léontos** (λέοντος) **m.** Gr.: lion].

Family Phyllodactylidae

phyllo- :« **phyllon** (φύλλον) **n.** Gr.: leaf + **dáktýlos** (δάκτυλος), *genet.* **daktýlou** (δάκτυλου) **m.** Gr.: finger, toe + **-idae pl.** L.: a suffix to form names of families of animals.

***Asaccus barani* Torki, Ahmadzadeh, Ilgaz, Avcı & Kumlutaş, 2011**

a- (ἀ-) Gr.: without + **saccus,-ī m.** L. :« **sákkos** (σάκκος) **m.** Gr.: coarse cloth of hair, anything made of coarse cloth like a sack or bag.

barani :« **Prof. Dr. İbrahim Baran** [b. 1940; K1sas, Ş.Urfa], Turkish herpetologist. He graduated from Ankara University, Faculty of Science (1963). He completed his doctorate under the supervision of Prof. Dr. Muhtar Başoğlu [q.v. ***Muhtarophis***] at the Department of Systematic Zoology, Ege University. He became an associate professor (1975) and professor (1981) at the same department. Later, he started to work at Dokuz Eylül University Buca Faculty of Education (1985) and continued to work there until his retirement (2007). There are many taxa dedicated to his name, e.g., *Neurergus barani* (salamander), *Eirenis barani* (snake), *Muhtarophis barani* (snake), *Anatololacerta ibrahimi* (lizard).

Family Gekkonidae (Geckoes)

gecko:« origin of the name is unclear; however, it originated from the Malay Archipelago [the name “gecko” was probably borrowed from the Dutch **gekko** in the 18th century into English and other European languages. In a Wikipedia note states that "some sources mentioned of a supposedly Malay **gekok**, **gekoq**, or **gekop** that imitates the chirping sound of the gecko lizard; another theory takes it from the Acehnese word gèh-gòh ("busy")] + **-idae pl.** L.: a suffix to form names of families of animals.

***Mediodactylus kotschy* (Steindachner, 1870)**

medio- NL. :« **mediō** Dat. **m./n. Sg.**, Abl. **m./n. Sg.** L. [« **medius,-a,-um** L.]: middle, mid, half, moderate + **dáktýlos** (δάκτυλος) Gr.: finger [q.v. **Phyllodactylidae**].

kotschyi, Kotschya, kotschyanus :« **Karl Georg Theodor Kotschy** [1813-1866], Austrian botanist, explorer and also son of botanist Karl Friedrich Kotschy [1789-1856]. He was born in Silesia (present-day Southern Poland). He collected more than 300,000 specimens on plant tours in the Middle East and North Africa, including Türkiye. He described numerous oak species. *Alburnus kotschyi* (fish), *Kotschya* (plant), *Ophrys kotschyi* (plant), and *Crocus kotschyanus* (plant) were named in his honor.

***Mediodactylus heterocercus* (Blanford, 1874)**

heterocerc- :« **héteros** (ἕτερος) **m.**, **hetérā** (ἑτέρᾱ) **f.**, **héteron** (ἕτερον) **n.** Gr.: other, another, different, one or the other of a pair + **kérkos** (κέρκος) **f.** Gr.: the tail of an animal, penis, handle.

***Mediodactylus danilewskii* (Strauch, 1887)**

danilewskii:« **Nikolai Danilewski** (also spelled **Nikolay Danilevsky**) [1822-1885], Russian naturalist, economist, ethnologist, philosopher, racist and historian. He also collected two specimens in type series of *Leuciscus danilewskii* (fish).

***Mediodactylus orientalis* (Stepáneek, 1937)**

orientālis,-e L. : of the east, eastern, rising [« **oriēns,-ntis m.** (*noun*) L.: east, sunrise, dawn, daybreak; **oriēns,-ntis** (*participle*): rising, appearing, originating + **-ālis m./f.** (**-āle n.**): a suffix, used to form adjectives of relationship from nouns or numerals]. The meaning and usage of “oriental” usually differs from Türkiye to China. It refers to the Levant, since its type material collected from Jerusalem, Israel.

***Cyrtopodion scabrum* (Heyden, 1827)**

cyrto- :« **kyrtós** (κῦρτός) **m.**, **kyrté** (κῦρτή) **f.**, **kyrtón** (κῦρτόν) **n.** Gr.: arched, vaulted humped, hunchbacked, convex + **pódion** (πόδιον) Gr.: small foot, foot of a vase [« diminutivus of **poús** (πούς) **m.** Gr.: foot],

scaber,-bra ,-brum L.: rough, scabrous, scabby.

***Hemidactylus turcicus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

hemi- NL. :« **hēmi-** (ἡμι-) Gr.: half (prefix) [« **hēmisus** (ἡμισυς) **m.** adj. Gr.: half] + **dáktýlos** (δάκτυλος) Gr.: finger [q.v. **Phyllodactylidae**],

turcicus,-a,-um ML. : Turkish, Türk.

***Stenodactylus grandiceps* Haas, 1952**

steno- : « **stenós** (στενός) **m.**, **stenē** (στενή) **f.**, **stenón** (στενόν) **n.** Gr.: narrow, tight + **dáktýlos** (δάκτυλος) Gr.: finger [q.v. **Phyllodactylidae**],

grandis,-e L. : large, big, great, grand, full-grown, old + **-ceps,-cipitis** L.: -headed.

Family Eublepharidae Boulenger, 1883

***Eublepharis angramainyu* Anderson & Leviton, 1966**

eu- NL. : « **eû-** (εὔ) Gr.: well, good (true) [« **eû** (εὔ) (indeclinable) Gr.: well « **eus** (εὖς) Gr.: good] + **blepharon,-ī** L. « **blépharon** (βλέφαρον) **n.** Gr.: eyelid]. The epithet refers to fully functional eyelids.

angramainyu: « **Angra Mainyu** the ancient Avestan language: a name for "Spirit of Darkness" or "destructive/evil spirit" according to Zoroastrians [« **Anra Mainiu**; « **anra**: evil + **mainiu**: spirit]. The name alludes to the nocturnal behaviour of the species.

Family Lacertidae (Lacertids)

lacerta,-ae f. L. : lizard + **-idae** *pl.* L.: a suffix to form names of families of animals.

***Acanthodactylus boskianus* (Daudin, 1802)**

acantho- NL. : with thorns, a spine or prickly fin; a spinous process of a vertebra [« **ákantha** (ἄκανθα) Gr.: thorn or **ákanthos** (ἄκανθος) Gr.: thorny bush; « **akē** (ἀκή): thorn + **ánthos** (ἄνθος): flower] + **dáktýlos** (δάκτυλος) Gr.: finger [q.v. **Phyllodactylidae**],

boskianus : « **Louis Augustin Guillaume Bosc** (or **Louis-Augustin Bosc d'Antic**) [1759–1828], French botanist, invertebrate zoologist, and entomologist.

***Acanthodactylus harranensis* Baran, Kumlutaş, Lanza, Sindaco, Ilgaz, Avcı & Crucitti, 2005**

harranensis,-e NL. : of or pertaining **Harran**, which is a district of Şanlıurfa Province in the southeast of Türkiye, at the Turkish-Syrian border.

***Acanthodactylus schreiberi* Boulenger, 1878**

schreiberi : « **Egid Schreiber** [1836-1913], Austrian zoologist. Author of *Herpetology Europaea* (1875).

***Acanthodactylus ilgazi* Kurnaz & Şahin, 2021**

ilgazi: « **Çetin Ilgaz**, Turkish herpetologist. He is a professor at Dokuz Eylul University in Izmir.

***Anatololacerta anatolica* (Werner, 1900)**

anatolicus,-a,-um L.: Anatolian [« **Anatolia,-ae** ML.: Anatolia, Asiatic Türkiye; « **anatólē** (ἀνατολή) Gr.: sunrise, a place from where the sun rises, the east; « **anatéllō** (ἀνατέλλω): to rise;

« **aná** (ἀνά): up + **téllō** (τέλλω): to perform, to rise), because Anatolia was east of Greece] + **lacerta**, -ae f. L.: lizard.

***Anatololacerta budaki* (Eiselt & Schmidtler, 1986)**

budaki: « **Prof. Dr. Abidin Budak** [b. 9 Kasım 1943; Dikili, İzmir], Turkish herpetologist and taxonomist. He attended primary and secondary school in Kınık and high school in İzmir Namık Kemal High School. He completed his undergraduate degree in 1968 and his doctorate in 1974 at Ege University, Faculty of Science, Department of Natural Sciences. He became associate professor in 1984 and professor in 1990. He retired from Ege University Science Faculty Biology Department Zoology Department in November 2010 [q.v. *Ablepharus budaki*].

***Anatololacerta danfordi* (Günther, 1876)**

danfordi, danfordii / danfordiae: « **Charles George Danford** [1843-1928], Scottish painter, lawyer, geologist, paleontologist, and ornithologist. He traveled to the Middle East and Abyssinia (1860-1890). He collected samples from different groups such as mammals, birds, fishes and plants from Türkiye (1875-1876 and 1879) and several taxa were dedicated to his name, e.g. *Anatololacerta danfordi* (lizard), *Anatolichthys danfordii* (fish). But *Crocus danfordiae* (plant) and *Iris danfordiae* (plant) was described in the name of his wife.

***Anatololacerta finikensis* (Eiselt & Schmidtler, 1986)**

finikensis, -e NL. : pertaining to **Finike** District of Antalya Province, in the southwest of Türkiye.

***Anatololacerta ibrahimi* (Eiselt & Schmidtler, 1986)**

ibrahimi : « **Prof. Dr. İbrahim Baran**, Turkish herpetologist [q.v. *Asaccus barani*].

***Anatololacerta pelasgiana* (Mertens, 1959)**

Pelasgia, -ae f. L. : « **Pelasgiā** (Πελασγία) f. Gr.: The region of Pelasgia (Pelasgians) from ancient communities; « **Pelasgós** (Πελασγός) m. Sg., **Pelasgoí** (Πελασγοί) m. pl. Gr.: Pelasgians was used by classical Greek writers generally for all the indigenous inhabitants of the Aegean Sea region. Before the arrival of the Greeks, they lived in the central and northern parts of their homeland of Greece, as well as on Crete and the Aegean islands.

***Apathya cappadocica* (Werner, 1902)**

apathia, -ae f. L. : freedom from passion or feeling; insensibility; stoicism [« **apátheia** (ἀπάθεια), genet. **apathéiās** (ἀπαθειᾶς) f. Gr.: insensibility, freedom from emotion; « **apathés** (ἀπαθής) m./f., **apathés** (ἀπαθής) n. Gr.: without feeling or suffering + -eia (-εια); « **a-** (ἀ-): not + **páthos** (πάθος) n. Gr.: feeling, suffering + -és (-ής) Gr.: adjective suffix]. The meaning of the genus name could

not be found. Probably derived from the word “**apathīa**” given above. This may indicate the dissimilarity of the new genus (originally the new subgenus) from the related lacertids. Perhaps it was an intellectual reference from author Lajos Méhely [1862–1953] of the breed, who died in prison at the age of 90 as a Nazi war criminal for 8 years.

cappadocicus, -a, -um L. : of or pertaining to Cappadocia; « **Cappadocia, -ae** f. L. [« **Kappadokiā** (Καππαδοκίᾱ), *genet.* **Kappadokiās** (Καππαδοκιάς) f. Gr.; « **katpatuka** Old Persian: possible meaning “low country”]; The ancient name of the region that covers the southern part of Sivas, the southern part of Yozgat, and the area between Kırşehir-Niğde-Malatya in Anatolia.

***Darevskia adjarica* (Darevsky & Eiselt, 1980)**

Darevskia: « **Dr. Ilya Sergeyevich Darevsky** [1924-2009], Russian zoologist, herpetologist. He was the first to discover the phenomenon of parthenogenesis in amniotic vertebrates in rock lizards. He also made important contributions to the understanding of the ecology, systematics and morphology of the *Lacerta saxicola* group of rock lizards. In 1997, the Spanish Arribas named the genus of rock lizards *Darevskia* and selected *D. saxicola* as the type species. Additionally, *Cyrtodactylus darevskii* (lizard), *Eutropis darevskii* (lizard), *Scincella darevskii* (lizard), and *Vipera darevskii* (snake) were named after his name.

adjarica NL. : « აჭარა (açara) Georgian: an autonomous republic of Georgia, with capital Batumi and located in its south-western corner, bordered by Türkiye to the south and by the Black Sea to the west. Predominantly populated by Muslim Georgians and Turks.

***Darevskia armeniaca* (Méhely, 1909)**

armeniacus, -a, -um L.: 1. dull orange; 2. Armenian [« **Armenia, -ae** f. Sg. L.: Armenia, related apricot (= **armeniaceum, -ī** n. L. = **mālum armeniaceum** L.) was spread throughout Roman Empire from Armenia].

***Darevskia bendimahiensis* (Schmidtler, Eiselt & Darevsky, 1994)**

bendimahiensis, -e NL. : pertaining to **Bendimahi** Valley, located in Muradiye District of Van Province, close to northeastern corner of Lake Van.

***Darevskia clarkorum* (Darevsky & Vedmederja, 1977)**

clarkorum *genet. pl.* NL. : « **Dr. Richard J. Clark** and **Erica D. Clark**. A herpetologist and ornithologist, Richard was a Professor of Biology at York College (Pennsylvania) and retired in 1998. They worked with his wife Erica and published "*Report on a Collection of Amphibians and*

Reptiles from Turkey" in 1973. Another species dedicated to the name of this couple is *Phrynocephalus clarkorum* (lizard).

***Darevskia derjugini* (Nikolsky, 1898)**

derjugini :« Prof. Dr. Konstantin Mikhailovich Deryugin (also spelled as **Derjugin**) [1878-1938], Hydrobiologist and oceanographer at the Leningrad State University. *Alburnus derjugini* (fish) was also dedicated to him.

***Darevskia bithynica* (Méhely, 1909)**

bithynicus,-a,-um L. : related with Bithynia; « **Bithynia,-ae** f. L.: the ancient name of the region between Bursa-İzmit-Bolu-Zonguldak.

***Darevskia rudis* (Bedriaga, 1886)**

rudis,-e L. : wild, coarse, rough, raw, uncultivated.

***Darevskia parvula* (Lantz & Cyrén, 1913)**

parvulus,-a,-um *dim.* L. : very little, tiny, petty; « **parvus,-a,-um** L.: small, little, puny.

***Darevskia praticola* (Eversmann, 1834)**

pratun,-ī n. L. : meadow + **-cola,-ae** m. L.: inhabitant, one who inhabits.

***Darevskia raddei* (Boettger, 1892)**

raddei :« Gustav Ferdinand Richard Radde [1831–1903], German naturalist and Siberian explorer. Some other taxa were dedicated to his name, e.g., *Sorex raddei* (Eulipotyphla) and *Montivipera raddei* (snake).

***Darevskia sapphirina* (Schmidtler, Eiselt & Darevsky, 1994)**

sapphīrinus,-a,-um L. : sapphirine; « **sapphīrus,-ī** f. L. [« **sáppheiros** (σάππειρος) f. Gr.]: sapphire, a precious stone in bluish color. It was named for its sapphire-like color in spots on its body.

***Darevskia tuniyevi* Arribas, Candan, Kurnaz, Kumlutaş, Caynak & Ilgaz, 2022**

tuniyevi :« Dr. Boris Sakoevich Tuniyev [b. 1956], Russian herpetologist from Federal State Institution Sochi National Park, Sochi (Russia). The name dedicated him for his remarkable work about the knowledge of Caucasian herpetofauna and its remarkable diversity.

***Darevskia salihae* Kurnaz, Şahin & Eroğlu, 2022**

salihae :« Saliha Şahin, who is the late mother of Mehmet Kürşat Şahin (Karaman, Türkiye), one of the authors.

***Darevskia unisexualis* (Darevsky, 1966)**

unisexualis,-e L. : single sexual, unisexual [« **ūni-** L.: one; « **ūnus,-a,-um** L.: one, single, alone + **sexualis,-e** L.: sexual]. The specific epithet refers that the species consists of females that reproduce by parthenogenesis.

***Darevskia uzzelli* (Darevsky & Danielyan, 1977)**

uzzelli :« **Thomas Marshall Uzzell, Jr.** [b. 1932], American herpetologist.

***Darevskia valentini* (Boettger, 1892)**

valentini:« **Jean Valentin** [1868–1898], naturalist associated with the Senckenberg Naturmuseum.

***Eremias pleskei* Nikolsky, 1905**

eremias :« **erēmía** (ἐρημία), *genet.* **erēmíās** (ἐρημιάς) **f.** Gr.: desert, solitude, uninhabited area, wilderness, loneliness [« **erêmos** (ἐρημος) Gr.: lonely, solitary + **-iā** (-iā): abstract noun suffix],
pleskei :« **Theodor Eduard Pleske** (Russian form: **Fedor Dmitrievitch Pleske**) [1858–1932], Russian ornithologist and entomologist working at the zoological museum in St. Petersburg. In 1880 he participated in an expedition to the Kola Peninsula. He was interested in birds and in 1881 he made collections that he donated to the Zoological Museum, where he worked under V.F. Russov and M.N. Bogdanov. In 1886 he became assistant to director A.A. Strauch [q.v. ***Blanus strauchi***]. He studied the bird collections of Russov from Turkmenistan. After 1918 he started working on insects (Diptera). After the death of V.L. Bianchi in 1920, he was appointed head of the Ornithology Department. He is believed to have been arrested in 1932. Some species were named to dedicate to him, e.g. *Podoces pleskei* (bird), *Helopsaltes pleskei* (bird), *Lagopus muta pleskei* (bird), and *Eremias pleskei* (lizard).

***Eremias strauchi* Kessler, 1878**

strauchii :« **Alexander Strauch**, Russian naturalist [q.v. ***Blanus strauchi***].

***Eremias suphani* Başoğlu & Hellmich, 1968**

Suphan, *genet.* **Suphani** NL. :« **Süphan Dağı** TR: Mount Süphan, which is a stratovolcano with an elevation of 4,058 metres. It is located in eastern Türkiye, just north of Lake Van.

***Iranolacerta brandtii* (De Filippi, 1863)**

Irano- :« **ایران** (irân) Persian: Iran (country, people) + **lacerta,-ae** **f.** L.: lizard,

brandtii, brandti :« **Johann Friedrich von Brandt** [1802–1879], Prussian surgeon, pharmacist, naturalist, mostly working in Russia. He was an entomologist specializing in paleontology and ornithology, as well as in the Coleoptera (insects) and Diplopoda (centipedes) groups. He

emigrated to Russia (1831) and was soon appointed director of the Zoological Museum of the St. Petersburg Academy of Sciences. He encouraged the collection of native animals not represented in the museum. *Myotis brandtii* (bat) and *Mesocricetus brandti* (Rodentia) were also named in his honor.

***Lacerta agilis* Linnaeus, 1758**

lacerta, -ae f. L.: lizard,

agilis, -e L. : nimble, agile, dextrous, quick, rapid, active, busy, easily or quickly movable.

***Lacerta media* Lantz & Cyrén, 1920**

medius, -a, -um L. : middle, mid, half, moderate.

***Lacerta pamphylica* Schmidtler, 1975**

pamphylicus, -a, -um L. : grown in Pamphylia, Pamphylia [« **Pamphylia**, -ae f. L.: the ancient name of the Antalya-Alanya region].

***Lacerta strigata* Eichwald, 1831**

strigātus, -a, -um L. : strigate, having transverse bands of colour [cf. **striga**, -ae f. L.: a strip, row, line].

***Lacerta diplochondrodes* Wettstein, 1952**

diplo- NL. : double [« **diplóos** (διπλόος) = **diploûs** (διπλοῦς) m. Gr.: double] + **chondródēs** (χονδροδῆς) Gr.: like groats, granular, like gristle, cartilaginous.

***Lacerta viridis* (Laurenti, 1768)**

viridis, -e L. : green; lively, young, fresh.

***Mesalina microlepis* (Angel, 1936)**

mesalina :« an euphonic name according to Agassiz (1846),

micro- NL. :« **mīkrós** (μικρός) m., **mīkrā** (μικρά) f., **mīkrón** (μικρόν) n. Gr.: little, small + **lepís** (λεπίς), genet. **lepídōs** (λεπίδος) f. Gr.: scale, flake, shell, husk.

***Ophisops elegans* Ménétries, 1832**

óphis (ὄφις), genet. **ópheōs** (ὄφεως) m. Gr.: a serpent, snake + **óps** (ὄψ), genet. **opós** (ὀπός) f. Gr.: eye; face, countenance],

ēlegāns, -ntis L. : gentle, thin, delicate, elegant.

***Parvilacerta parva* (Boulenger, 1887)**

parvus, -a, -um L. : small, little, puny + **lacerta**, -ae f. L.: lizard.

***Phoenicolacerta cyaniparsa* (Schmidtler & Bischoff, 1999)**

phoeniceus,-a,-um L. : « **phoinīkeos** m. Y.: purple-red or crimson [=purpleus] [« **phoenix** (φοῖνῖξ), *genet.* **phoinīkos** (φοῖνῖκος) m. Gr.: purple or crimson] + **lacerta,-ae** f. L.: lizard,
cyanus,-ī = cyanos,-ī m. L. : a precious stone with dark blue-green in colour, blue cornflower [« **kyáneos** (κυάνεος) m. Gr.; « **kyanos** (κῦάνος) m. Gr.: dark, dark-blue] + **sparsus,-a,-um** L.: scattered, strewn, sprinkled spotted, freckled.

***Phoenicolacerta laevis* (Gray, 1838)**

laevis,-e = levis,-e L. : smooth; also light, easy.

***Podarcis muralis* (Laurenti, 1768)**

podarcis : « **podárkēs** (ποδάρκης) m./f., **pódarkes** (ποδάρκες) n. Gr.: strong of foot, swift-footed, having swift runners [« **poús** (πούς) m. Gr.: foot + **arkéō** (ἀρκέω) Gr.: run to assist + **-ēs** (-ης) Gr.: adjectival suffix],

mūrālis,-e = murarius,-a,-um L. : (relational) wall (especially of city walls); « **mūrus,-ī** m.: wall.

***Podarcis siculus* (Rafinesque-Schmaltz, 1810)**

siculus,-a,-um L. : Sicilian [cf. **sīcula,-ae** f. *dim.* L.: small dagger].

***Podarcis tauricus* (Pallas, 1814)**

tauricus,-a,-um L. : Crimean; « **Tauria,-ae** f. = **Taurica** L. [« **Taurikê** (Ταυρικῆ) Gr.: Crimea.

***Timon kurdistanicus* (Suchow, 1936)**

Timon : « The origin of the name is unclear, but it may be derived from **Timon of Athens** (*The Life of Timon of Athens*), a five-act play by the English writer William SHAKESPEARE, must be related to the play. Similarly, John Edward GRAY derived some taxon names from other theatrical works. For example, Gray (1870) derived the genus names *Azema* (now a synonym for *Microcebus*), *Mirza*, and *Phaner* from the Lemurs (Primates), inspired by yet another theatrical play.

kurdistanicus NL. : « related with Persian **کردستان** (Kordestân), a political term.

Family Scincidae (Skinks)

scincus,-ī = scincos,-ī m. L. : « **skínkos** (σκίγκος) = **skíngos** (σκίγγος) m. Gr.: a skink, a kind of lizard + **-idae** *pl.* L.: a suffix to form names of families of animals.

***Ablepharus bivittatus* (Ménétries, 1832)**

ablepharus : « **ablépharos** (ἀβλέφαρος) Gr.: without eyebrows, without eyelids [« **a-** (ἀ-) Gr.: not, without + **blepharon,-ī** L. « **blépharon** (βλέφαρον) n. Gr.: eyelid],

bivittātus,-a,-um NL. : having two bands or stripes [« **bi-** L.: having two parts occurring twice; « **bis** (not comparable) L.: twice, two times, in two ways; « **duo** L.: two (II) + **vittātus,-a,-um** L.: banded, striped [« **vitta,-ae** f. L.: band, ribbon, headband, fillet].

***Ablepharus budaki* Göçmen, Kumlutaş & Tosunoğlu, 1996**

budaki :« Prof. Dr. Abidin Budak, Turkish herpetologist [q.v. *Anatololacerta budaki*].

***Ablepharus chernovi* Darevsky, 1953**

chernovi :« **Sergueï Aleksandrovitch Tchernov** (or **Chernov**) [1903-1964], Soviet herpetologist. He studied at Karkhov University until 1926, especially with Alexander Nikolski [1858-1942]. He became the curator of the department of herpetology, replacing Sergei Tsarevski in the zoological museum of the Leningrad Academy of Sciences (1930). He studied the fauna of beyond the Caspian Sea (1932), the Caucasus (1937-1939) and Tajikistan (1942-1944). Among his many publications, he co-authored "Synopsis des Reptiles et des Amphibiens d'URSS" (Summary of Reptiles and Amphibians of the USSR) with Pavel Terentiev [1903-1970] in three Russian editions (1936, 1940 and 1949) and a translation into English (1965). His student Iliia S. Darevski [1925-2009] replaced him as head of the department of herpetology.

***Ablepharus kitaibelii* (Bibron & Bory St-Vincent, 1833)**

Kitaibelia / kitaibelii :« **Pál Kitaibel** [1757-1817], Hungarian botanist and chemist. He studied botany and chemistry at the University of Buda. He became a professor in 1794. Hungary commemorated him and his lizard with a postage stamp. Some of the taxons dedicated to his name are *Kitaibelia* (plant), *Ablepharus kitaibelii* (lizard), and *Aquilegia kitaibelii* (plant).

***Chalcides ocellatus* (Forskål, 1775)**

chalcis,-idis f. L. :« **khalkís** (χᾱλκίς), *genet.* **khalkídos** (χᾱλκίδος) f. Gr.: a kind of fish, possibly a sardine or herring; a lizard with copper-colored spots on its back; and also, European Roller (*Coracias garrulus*) [« **khalkós** (χαλκός) m. Gr.: copper, bronze + **-ís** (-ίς) Gr.: suffix forms female nouns],

ocellātus,-a,-um L. : having small eyes.

***Eumeces schneiderii* (Daudin, 1802)**

eu- NL. :« **eû-** (εὖ) Gr.: well, good [q.v. *Eublepharis*] + **mēkos** (μήκος), *genet.* **mēkous** (μήκουσ) n. Attic = **mēkeos** (μήκεος) or **mēkeus** (μήκευσ) n. Ionic: length, greatness, size (length, height, greatness, magnitude, etc.),

schneiderii :« **Johann Gottlob Theaenus Schneider** [1750-1822], German classicist and naturalist. In 1774, on the recommendation of Christian Gottlob Heine, he became secretary of the famous Strasbourg scholar Richard François Brunck, professor of ancient languages and rhetoric at Breslau in 1811, and chief librarian in 1816.

***Ophiomorus kardesi* Kornilios, Kumlutaş, Lymberakis & Ilgaz, 2018**

ophio- :« **óphis** (ὄφις) **m.** Gr.: a serpent, snake [q.v. *Ophisops*] + **hómoros** (ὄμορος) **m./f.**, **hómoron** (ὄμορον) **n.** Gr.: bordering, having the same borders with, bordering on, neighboring, neighbour; near, closely resembling. Duméril & Bibron (1839) describe *Ophiomorus* as a new genus (p. 799); explained the allusion in Latin and French as follows: “*De oφις, Serpent, et de ομορος confinis, sibi ipsi particeps - ayant beaucoup de ressemblance*”. It refers to the resemblance of this genus to a snake.

kardesi :« **kardeş** TR: sibling, brother, sister, or best friend. The species epithet is a genitive noun of this Turkish word. As a word, it is used in both Türkiye and Greece with the same meaning. It is used here to highlight the sibling-species relationship between the new species and *O. punctatissimus*, to emphasize the past and contemporary role of the Aegean Sea as cradle of speciation and to mark a decade of collaboration and friendship among the authors.

***Heremites auratus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

heremit- :« **erēmítēs** (ἐρημίτης) Gr.: of the desert [« **erēmíā** (ἐρημίᾱ), *genet.* **erēmíās** (ἐρημίᾱς) **f.** Gr.: desert, uninhabited area, wilderness; solitude, loneliness [« **erêmos** (ἐρημος) **m.**: lonely + **-íā** (-ῖᾱ): abstract noun suffix]; » **erēmítīs** (herēmitis), **-idis f.** L.: hermit, loner, solitary, **aurātus,-a,-um** L. (ppr.) : ornamented with gold, gilded, colored with gold, gold-colored; (adj.): golden, gilded; « **aurum,-ī n.**: gold.

***Heremites vittatus* (Olivier, 1804)**

vittātus,-a,-um: banded, striped [« **vitta,-ae f.** L.: band, ribbon, headband, fillet].

***Heremites septemtaeniatus* (Reuss, 1834)**

septem- (*indeclinable*) L. : seven (VII = 7) + **taeniātus,-a,-um** L.: beribboned.

Family Varanidae

***Varanus griseus* (Daudin, 1803)**

varanus NL. :« **varan** Fr. [« **وَرَان** (waran) Ar.]: monitor lizard, **grīseus,-a,-um** NL. : grey.

Family Anguidae (Glass Lizards)

***Anguis colchica* (Nordmann, 1840)**

anguis,-is m. L. : snake, serpent, dragon,

colchicus,-a,-um L. : of or pertaining to Colchis [« **Colchis,-idis** f. Sg. L. [« **Kolkhís** (Κολχίς), *genet.* **Kolkhídos** (Κολχίδος) f. Gr.], an ancient region and kingdom on the coast of the Black Sea, corresponding to what is now western Georgia.

***Pseudopus apodus* (Pallas, 1775)**

pseudo- NL.: prefix with meaning “pseudo-, false, untrue, not genuine, fake, similar [««« **pseudēs** (ψευδής) Gr.: false, lying; «« **pseudō** (ψεύδω) Gr.: to lie] + **poús** (πούς) m. Gr.: foot, leg
a- (ἀ-) Gr.: without + **podós** (ποδός), genitivus of **poús** (πούς) m. Gr.: foot, leg

Suborder Serpentes Linnaeus, 1758 (Snakes)

serpēns,-ntis m./f.; **serpentes** Nom., Acc., Voc. *pl. (noun)* L. : a serpent, snake, any creeping animal, louse; **serpēns,-ntis** (*participle*): sinuous, coiled like a snake; « **serp/ō, -ere, serpsī, serptum** [*no passivum*]: crawl, creep slowly, crawl on all fours (3rd declension).

Family Leptotyphlopidae (Slender Blind Snakes)

leptus,-a,-um NL. :« **leptós** (λεπτός) m. Gr.: thin, slender + **typhlops**: blind eyed [q.v. **Typhlopidae**] + **-idae** *pl.* L.: a suffix to form names of families of animals.

***Myriopholis macrorhyncha* (Jan, 1860)**

myríos (μυρίος) m., **mýriā** (μυριά) f., **mýrion** (μυρίον) n. Gr.: many, countless, numberless, ten thousand + **pholís** (φολίζ), *genet.* **pholídos** (φολίδος) f. Gr.: 1. horny scale (of reptiles), 2. spot on a leopard’s skin; in allusion to the high number of middorsal and subcaudal scales typical of species in this genus (Adalsteinsson et al., 2009).

macr(o)- :« **makrós** (μακρός) m., **makrā** (μακρά) f., **makrón** (μακρόν) n. Gr.: long, tall, deep, far + **rhyncha** « **rhýnkhos** (ρύγκος), *genet.* **rhýnkhou** (ρύγκου) n. Gr.: snout, the nose of an animal, muzzle beak of a bird, bill; referring to the relatively long snout of the species (Adalsteinsson et al., 2009).

Family Typhlopidae (Blind Snakes)

typhl- :« **typhlós** (τυφλός) m., **typhlē** (τυφλή) f., **typhlón** (τυφλόν) n. Gr.: blind, unseen, obscure + **óps** (ὄψ), *genet.* **opós** (ὀπός) f.: eye, face + **-idae** *pl.* L.: a suffix to form names of families of animals.

***Xerotyphlops vermicularis* (Merrem, 1820)**

xērós (ξηρός) **m.**, **xērā** (ξηρά) **f.**, **xērón** (ξηρόν) **n.** Gr.: dry + **typhlops**: blind eyed [q.v. **Typhlopidae**],

vermiculāris,-e NL.: a specific epithet of many taxonomic species names; « **vermiculus,-ī m.** *dim.* L.: little worm, grub) + **-aris** (adjectival suffix): the former being the diminutive of **vermis,-is m.**: worm.

Letheobia episcopa(Franzen & Wallach, 2002)

An allusion to *Letheobia* Cope, 1868 is not explained (Cope, 1868). Possibly related with possibly referring to the underground secluded life of snakes of this genus. **lethe** (usually uncountable, *pl. lethes*) L.: 1. forgetfulness of the past; oblivion; 2. (obsolete, rare) death [« **Lēthē,-ēs f.** *Sg.* L.: (Greek mythology) the river Lethe, the river of oblivion; « **Lēthē** (Λήθη), *genet.* **Lēthēs** (Λήθης) **f.** Gr.: the river Lethe, and a naiad nymph in Greek mythology; **Lethe** NL.: (Greek mythology) 1. The personification of oblivion, daughter of Eris; 2. the river which flows through Hades from which the souls of the dead drank so that they would forget their time on Earth; » **lēthaios** (λήθαιος), **lēthaíos** (ληθαῖος) Gr. » **Lēthaeus,-a,-um** L.: of or pertaining to Lethe, Lethean; of the underworld, of the infernal regions, causing forgetfulness or sleepiness + **bíos** (βίος), *genet.* **bíou** (βίου) **m.** Gr.: life [cf. **bíā** (βίᾱ), *genet.* **bías** (βιάς) **f.** Gr.: bodily strength, force; act of violence]. **episcopus,-ī m.** LL. : bishop; « **epískopos** (ἐπίσκοπος) **m.** Gr.: watcher, guardian, supervisor, inspector, scout [« **epí-** (ἐπί-) Gr.: upon) + **skopós** (σκοπός) Gr.: watcher, lookout, guardian; « **bischof** German: bishop]. Dedication to the German herpetologist **Wolfgang Bischoff** from ZFMK (Bonn), who collected most of the type material.

Family Boidae (Boas)

boa,-ae f. L. : a large snake native to Roman Italy + **-idae** *pl.* L.: a suffix to form names of families of animals.

Eryx jaculus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Eryx, *genet.* **Erycis m.** *Sg.* L. : « **Éryx** (Ἐρυξ), *genet.* **Érykos** (Ἐρύκος) **m.** Gr.: A mountain in the northwest of Sicily with a famous temple of Venus on its top, and the name of the city [*the genus name of the snake derives from here*] [cf. **Eryx**, the unnamed hero who is also the son of Venus, defeated by Heracles in a struggle],

jaculus,-a,-um = iaculus,-a,-um (*adj.*) L.: that is thrown (arrow, dart etc); **jaculus,-a,-um = iaculus,-a,-um** (*noun*): a serpent that darts from a tree onto its prey [« **jacul/or, -ārī, (-ārier), jaculātus sum** [= **iacul/or, -ārī (-ārier), iaculātus sum**] L.: javelin, or throw, to fight with the

javelin; splash (deponens; 1st declension) to throw, hurl, cast, fling; throw away = **iac/iō, -ere, iēcī, iactum** [= **jac/iō, -ere, jēcī, jactum**] L.: to throw [« **jaculum, -ī n. = iaculum, -ī n.**: a dart, a javelin + **-ō**].

Family Natricidae

Natrix natrix (Linnaeus, 1758)

natrīx, -icis f. L. : water snake; « **nat/ō, -āre, natāvī, natātum**: y swim, float, flow (1st declension); « **n/ō, -āre, nāvī** [no *passivum and supinum*]: yüzmek (1st declension).

Natrix tessellata (Laurenti, 1768)

tessellātus, -a, -um L.: made of small square stones (*mosaic or pavement*) [« **tessella, -ae f.**: small cube; « **tessera, -ae f.**: mosaic piece, dice piece (*in backgammon*)].

Family Colubridae (Colubrids)

coluber, -ī m. L. : snake + **-idae pl. L.**: a suffix to form names of families of animals.

Coronella austriaca Laurenti, 1768

corona, -ae f. L. : crown, chaplet + **-ella**: diminutive suffix,
austriacus, -a, -um L. : Austrian, raised in Austria; « **Austria, -ae f. Sg. NL.**: Austria.

Dolichophis caspius (Gmelin, 1789)

dolicho- :« **dolikhós** (δολιχός) **m.**, **dolikhé** (δολιχή) **f.**, **dolikhón** (δολιχόν) **n.** Gr.: long, longish + **óphis** (ὄφις) **m.** Gr.: a serpent, snake [q.v. *Ophisops*],

Caspus, -a, -um L. :« **Káspios** (Κάσπιος) Gr.: Caspian Sea, related to Caspia.

Dolichophis jugularis (Linnaeus, 1758)

iugulāris, -e L. = jugulāris, -e LL.: (relational) jugular; « **iugulum, -ī n. L. = jugulum, -ī n. LL.**: the collarbone; the hollow part of the neck above the collarbone [« **iugum, -ī n. L. = jugum, -ī n. LL.**: a yoke (for oxen) or collar (for a horse)] + **-āris** (“-ar, -ary”, adjectival suffix).

Dolichophis schmidti (Nikolsky, 1909)

schmidti :« **Prof. Petr Yulievich Schmidt** [1872-1949], an ichthyologist at the Zoological Museum and Institute in St. Petersburg. He published “Fishes of Eastern Seas of the Russian Empire” in 1904. *Petroschmidtia* (fish), *Cottiusculus schmidti* (fish), and *Dolichophis schmidti* (snake) were dedicated to his honor, although the patronym is not specified, it probably belongs to this ichthyologist.

Eirenis aurolineatus (Venzmer, 1919)

eiren- :« **eirēnē** (εἰρήνη) Gr.: peace, time of peace; » **Eirēnē** (Εἰρήνη) Gr. [» **Īrēnē**, *genet.* **Īrēnēs** f. Sg. L.]: Irene (Greek goddess of peace and plenty, Latin equivalent: Pax)],

auro- NL. : relating to gold [« **aurum,-ī n.** L.: gold, gold colour, an object made of gold] + **lineatus,-a,-um**: striped [« **-linea,-ae f.** L.: line, border [**lineatus** NL.: The unit of measure is 2.1167 mm in the English system and 2.325 mm in the French system].

***Eirenis barani* Schmidtler, 1988**

barani :« **Prof. Dr. İbrahim Baran**, Turkish herpetologist [q.v. *Asaccus barani*].

***Eirenis collaris* (Ménétries, 1832)**

collare,-is n. LL. : collar, neckband; necklace; « **collus,-ī m.** = **collum,-ī n.** L.: neck or throat; » **collis** NL.: collar, necklace, ring [*Dat., Abl.* from **collum**].

***Eirenis coronella* (Schlegel, 1837)**

corona,-ae f. L. : crown, wreath + **-ella**: diminutive suffix

***Eirenis decemlineatus* (Duméril, Bibron & Duméril, 1854)**

decem (indeclinable) L. : ten (X = 10) + **-lineatus,-a,-um** L.: striped [q.v. *Eirenis aurolineatus*].

***Eirenis eiselti* Schmidtler & Schmidtler 1978**

eiselti :« **Dr. Josef Eiselt** [1912–2001], Austrian herpetologist. He started to learn the University of Vienna (1933) where he completed his doctorate (1939) with a thesis on comparative amphibian ear anatomy. He was a British POW until the end of the Second World War (1945). Then he was a school teacher (1949-1951). He became curator of the herpetology department of the Natural History Museum in Vienna (1952) and retired in 1977. He was elected the first president of Societas Europaea Herpetologica and held that position until 1985. He made specimen collection trips to Africa and especially Southwest Asia. During his retirement he visited Türkiye again and made a total of 15 trips there. The following are some of the taxa named in his honor: *Calamaria eiselti* (snake), *Emys orbicularis eiselti* (turtle), *Eirenis eiselti* (snake), *Pseudorabdion eiselti* (snake).

***Eirenis thospitis* Schmidtler & Lanza, 1990**

Thospītēs,-ae m.; **Thospītis,-is f.** (**Thospitis Lacus**) L. :« **Thospitis limne** (Θωσπιτις λίμνη) Gr.: Urartian name of Lake Van.

***Eirenis hakkariensis* Schmidtler & Eiselt, 1991**

hakkariensis,-e NL. : belongs to or pertaining to **Hakkâri** Province in the southeast of Türkiye.

***Eirenis levantinus* Schmidtler, 1993**

levantinus,-a,-um NL. : pertaining to Levant; « **Levant**: Eastern Mediterranean 1. Syria, Lebanon, Israel, Palestine, Jordan and Cyprus; and sometimes, especially historically, the region that was once part of the Ottoman Empire, including Türkiye and Egypt; 2. an easterly wind that usually blows in the western Mediterranean; « **levans,-ntis** L. : lifting, raising; » **levant** Fr.: rising, sunrise point.

***Eirenis lineomaculatus* Schmidt, 1939**

lineo- : « **linea,-ae f.** L.: line, border [q.v. *Eirenis aurolineatus*] + **maculatus,-a,-um**: blotchy, spotted ; « **maculō, -āre, maculāvī, maculātum**: stain, pollute (1st declension); « **macula,-ae f.** L.: (*large*) blotch, spot.

***Eirenis modestus* (Martin, 1838)**

modestus,-a,-um; *Comp.* **modestior,-ius**; *Sup.* **modestissimus,-a,-um**; *adv.* **modestē** (*Comp.*, **modestius**, *Sup.* **modestissimē**) L. : moderate, calm, restrained, modest, reserved, prudent, reasonable, well-behaved ; « **modus,-ī m.**; *dim.* **modulus,-ī m.** L.: measure, scale.

***Eirenis punctatolineatus* (Boettger, 1892)**

pūnctātus,-a,-um L.: dotted + **-lineatus,-a,-um** L.: striped [q.v. *Eirenis aurolineatus*].

***Eirenis occidentalis* Rajabizadeh, Nagy, Adriaens, Avcı, Masroor, Schmidtler, Nazarov, Esmaili & Christiaens, 2015**

occidentālis,-e L. : located in the west, western.

***Eirenis rothii* Jan, 1863**

rothii : « **Johannes Rudolph Roth** [1814–1858], German naturalist. He studied medicine and natural sciences and accompanied Gotthilf Heinrich von Schubert's expedition to Egypt and Palestine in 1836-37. In 1839 he traveled to the East Indies and the northwest coast of Africa. In 1843 he became a professor of zoology at the University of Munich. He made two more expeditions to Palestine in 1852 and 1856. Died of fever in Anti-Lebanon and was buried in Jerusalem.

***Elaphe dione* (Pallas, 1773)**

elaph- : « **elaphê** (ἐλαφή) **f.** Gr.: 1. deerskin; 2. name of a snake described by Nicandre of Colophon [B.C. II. century] [« **elaphus,-ī m.** NL. « **élaphos** (ἔλαφος) **m./f.** Gr.: deer, red deer], **dione** : « **Diōnē** (Διώνη) Gr.: The name was given to four women in Greek Mythology [means "female Zeus" and Zeus' genitivus can be translated from Dios as "goddess". Name of a serpent,

often described by the goddess of love, Aphrodite (=mother or sometimes identified as herself) of the Romans Venus].

***Elaphe sauromates* (Pallas, 1811)**

sauromatēs, -ae m. L. : « **Sauromátēs** (Σαυρομάτης) = **Sarmátēs** (Σαρμάτης) Gr.: Sarmatians [As can be seen from the Turkish vernacular name "Sarı Yılan" (Yellow Snake), this species has a yellowish coloration. Thus, the name may have come from both the Sarmatians, known in ancient Greece as 'yellow-haired' ones, and their ancient country Sarmatía (Σαρματία), which is type locality of this species].

***Elaphe urartica* Jablonski, Kukushkin, Avcı, Bunyatova, Ilgaz, Tuniyev & Jandzik, 2019**

urartica NL. : Urartian; « **Urartu NL.** « **Urartu** Akkadian: An Iron Age kingdom that flourished in 9th-6th century BC and centred in the mountainous area around Lake Van and extending to the Erzurum-Kars Plateau, in eastern Türkiye.

***Hemorrhois nummifer* (Reuss, 1834)**

hemorrhois : « **haimorrhōís** (αἰμορροΐς) **f. Sg.** Gr.: haemorrhoid [« **haimórrhoos** (αἰμόρροος) Gr.: flowing with blood; « **haimo-** (αἰμο-) [« **haîma** (αἷμα) **n.** Gr.: blood] + **rhéō** (ρέω) Gr.: flow [cf. **haîma** + **órrhos** (ὄρρος) **m.** Gr.: butt, ass],

nummus, -ī m. L. : specie, coins; » **nummularius, -a, -um:** coin-like; » **nummifer(us), -fera, -ferum:** bearer of coins [« **fer(us), -fera, -ferum** L.: carrying, bringing]. The name is a reference to coin-like spots on the back.

***Hemorrhois ravergeri* (Ménétries, 1832)**

ravergeri : « **Mr. Raverger** [fl. 1830], attached at the French embassy in St. Petersburg, Russia.

***Platyceps collaris* (Müller, 1878)**

platy- NL. : « **platýs** (πλατύς) **m.** Gr.: flat + **-ceps, -cipitis** L.: -headed, **collare, -is n.** LL.: collar, neckband; necklace [q.v. *Eirenis collaris*].

***Platyceps najadum* (Eichwald, 1831)**

naias, genet. naiadis f. = nais, genet. naidis L. : « **nāiás** (ναῖάς), **genet. nāiádos** (ναῖάδος) **f. = naiáda** (ναῖάδα) **f.** Gr.: naiad, river nymph [« **náein** (νάειν) Gr.: to flow]. No explanation was given as to the name of the snake; it probably got its name from these fairies, also called “*naiadum pulcherrima*”; pulcherrima: the most beautiful.

***Platyceps rhodorachis* (Jan, 1863)**

rhodo- NL. : « **rhódon** (ρόδον) n. Gr.: rose (color) “red” + **rhachis** (**rachis**) NL. « **rhákhis** (ράχης), *genet.* **rhákhios** (ράχιος) / **rhákheōs** (ράχεως) f.; *dim.* **rhákhion** Gr.]: spine, backbone, ridge. The name of the species; possibly implies a reddish (rose) stripe along its spine.

***Platyceps ventromaculatus* (Gray, 1834)**

ventro- NL. : « abdomen; « **-venter,-tris** m. L.: belly, stomach; » **ventrālis,-e**: ventral; of or pertaining to the belly + **maculatus,-a,-um**: spotted, blotched [q.v. *Eirenis lineomaculatus*].

The status of *P. ventromaculatus* in Türkiye is controversial. Turkish specimens may belong to ***Platyceps karelini* (Brandt, 1838)** (see Jablonski et al., 2022).

karelini : « **Grigory Silych** (or **Grigori Silich** or **Grigorij Silyc**) **Karelin** [1801–1872], a Russian explorer and naturalist who traveled throughout Siberia and Central Asia. Many plant species were identified from the specimens he collected (Beolens et al., 2013). Some taxa were dedicated to his name, e.g. *Karelinia* (plant), *Platyceps karelini* (snake), and *Triturus karelinii* (newt).

***Muhtarophis barani* Olgun, Avcı, Ilgaz, Üzüm & Yılmaz, 2007**

Muhtarophis : « **Prof. Dr. Muhtar Başoğlu** [1913-1981], the first Turkish herpetologist and taxonomist [some taxa dedicated by surname, e.g. *Entodinium basoglui* (Alveolata: Ciliophora), *Lyciasalamandra luschani basoglui* (salamander), and *Ophisops elegans basoglui* (lizard)] + **óphis** (ὄφις) m. Gr.: a serpent, snake [q.v. *Ophisops*],

barani : « **Prof. Dr. İbrahim Baran**, Turkish herpetologist [q.v. *Asaccus barani*].

***Rhynchocalamus melanocephalus* (Jan, 1862)**

rhynchus NL. : « **rhýnkhos** (ρύγχος), *genet.* **rhýnkhou** (ρύγχου) n. Gr.: snout, the nose of an animal, muzzle, bill, beak of a bird [cf. **rhīs** (ρίς), *genet.* **rhīnós** (ρῖνός) f. Gr.: nose or snout of men and beasts]; (in the plural) nostrils + **calamus,-ī** m. L.; « **kálamos** (κάλαμος) Gr.: reed, cane, things like pen made from reed and cane,

melanocephalus,-a,-um NL. : having a black head [« **mélās** (μέλας) m., **mélaina** (μέλαινα) f., **mélan** (μέλαν) n., *genet.* **mélanos** (μέλανος) m./n., **melaínēs** (μελαίνης) f. Gr.: dark, black + **-cephalus,-a,-um** NL.: headed [q.v. *Phrynocephalus horvathi*].

***Rhynchocalamus satunini* (Nikolsky, 1899)**

satunini : « **Konstantin Alekseevich Satunin** [1863–1915], Russian zoologist who studied and described many mammals found in the Caucasus, Russia, and Central Asia.

***Spalerosophis diadema* (Schlegel, 1837)**

Allusion for the genus name is not explained. Its name spalerosophis is thought to have been mispronounced as a result of the lapsus calami of sphalerosophis. Likewise, Marx (1959) says "*the spelling of the generic name has been in question. In the original description of the genus (Jan, 1865) the name is given as Spalerosophis, but in the following description of the type species the generic name is spelled Sphalerosophis. The first spelling, Spalerosophis, is here retained, due to page priority; this spelling is most familiar in the literature*" on this subject. The pronunciation of the genus name was discussed by the ICZN (1966) under Opinion 794, taking into account the opinion of Marx (1959), the first reviser, and the use of the name *Sphalerosophis* Jan, 1865 was rejected by majority vote.

sphalero- :« **sphalerós** (σφαλερός) Gr.: slippery, perilous, deceiving, treacherous, likely to make one stumble ready to fall, reeling, tottering [cf. **spaleís** (σπάλεις) [passive of **stéllō** (στέλλω)]: to make ready, prepare; to furnish, dress; to dispatch, send; to set out, to gather up]; « **sphállō** (σφάλλω) Gr.: to topple, overthrow to kill to baffle (active); to be foiled, to fall, to be cast down (from a figurative or literal elevated place) to stagger, reel (passive) + **-rós** (-ρός) Gr.: + **óphis** (ὄφις) **m.** Gr.: a serpent, snake [q.v. *Ophisops*],

diadēma,-atis n. L. : reign, crown; royal headdress [« **diádēma** (διάδημα), *genet.* **diadēmatos** (διᾶδήματος) **n.** Gr.: headband, decorative wreath-shaped headdress, crown; « **diadéō** (διαδέω) Gr.: to bind round + **-ma** (-μα) Gr.: result noun suffix].

Telescopus fallax Fleischmann, 1831

tele- :« **tēle** (τῆλε) Gr.: far off, afar, far away [cf. **teleios** (τέλειος) = **teleos** (τέλεος): fully grown; adult; « **télos** (τέλος): end] + **skopós** (σκοπός) **m.** Gr.: watcher, lookout protector, guardian; « **skopéō** (σκοπέω) Gr.: to look at [cf. **scopus,-ī m.** L.: a target],

fallax,-acis L. : deceptive, deceitful, fallacious; « **fall/ō, -ere, fefellī, falsum**: betray, deceive, cheat, disappoint, perjury, stumble, to deceive (3rd declension)].

Telescopus nigriceps (Ahl, 1924)

nigriceps,-cipitis NL. : black-headed [« **niger,-gra,-grum** L.: black + **-ceps,-cipitis** L.: -headed].

Zamenis hohenackeri (Strauch, 1873)

zamenis :« **zamenēs** (ζᾶμενής) Gr.: very strong, mighty, raging, hostile, strong, fierce of things (= **vehemens** L., **iracundus** L.) [« **zá** (ζά) Gr.: very + **ménos** (μένος) Gr.: might, force, strength, fierceness, courage, martial fury, rage],

hohenackeri :« **Rudolph Friedrich Hohenacker** [1798-1874], Swiss-German missionary and botanist. He collected plant samples in the Caucasus. Apart from this snake, it is also dedicated to taxa such as *Hohenackeria* (plant) and *Alburnus hohenackeri* (fish) (Karataş & Karataş, 2022; ETYFish 2022)].

Zamenis longissimus (Laurenti, 1768)

longissimus, -a, -um *Sup. L.* : longest, very long; furthest, very far [« **longus, -a, -um** L.: long, far].

Zamenis situla (Linnaeus, 1758)

situlus, -ī m. = situla, -ae f. L. = situlum, -ī n. ML. : bucket, container for drawing water from the well, cube, jar.

Family Lamprophiidae

lampr- :« **lamprós** (λαμπρός) **m.** Gr.: bright, radiant + **-óphis** (ὄφις) **m.** Gr.: a serpent, snake [q.v. *Ophisops*] + **-idae** *pl.* L.: a suffix to form names of families of animals.

Malpolon insignitus (Geoffroy Saint-Hilaire, 1827)

malpolon :« possibly Tamil, Sri Lankan name of a snake species. The patterned snake, which John Ray and Albertus Seba referred to as the "most wanted snake" with the name malpolon before the binary naming, is perhaps the genus name given to the deep-headed snake by Fitzinger in 1826, from the name of a python,

īnsgnītus, -a, -um L.: marked, distinctive; « **īnsgnis, -e**: unique, well-marked, outstanding.

Family Viperidae (Vipers and Pit Vipers)

Daboia palaestinae (Werner, 1938)

daboia Hindi (Sinhalese) name meaning "the lurker" or "that lies hid".

palaestinae :« **Palaestina, -ae f. L.** [« **Palaistínē** (Παλαιστίνη), *genet.* **Palaistínēs** (Παλαιστίνης) *f. Gr.*]: Palestine.

Macrovipera lebetinus (Linnaeus, 1758)

macr(o)- :« **makrós** Gr.: long, tall [q.v. *Myriopholis macrorhyncha*] + **vipera, -ae f. L.**: snake, **lebetinus** NL.: adjective of unknown meaning. There are two different views in the Reptile Database: referring to its origin in the Levant or referring to Greek funeral drummers ("lebes" or similar), it means a warning.

Montivipera raddei (Boettger, 1890)

mons, -montis m. L. : mountain + **vipera, -ae f. L.**: snake,

raddei :« **Gustav Ferdinand Richard Radde** [q.v. *Darevskia raddei*].

***Montivipera wagneri* (Nilson & Andrén, 1984)**

wagneri :« **Moritz Wagner** [1813-1887], German explorer, collector, geographer, and natural historian. He devoted three years (1836-1839) to the exploration of Algeria. It was here that he made important observations in natural history and developed his ideas that geographic isolation could play an important role in speciation. He traveled with Carl Scherzer in North and Central America and the Caribbean (1852-1855). He toured Armenia (1843) and collected the type specimen of *M. wagneri* in 1846. Moritz committed suicide in Munich.

***Montivipera bulgardaghica* (Nilson & Andrén, 1985)**

bulgardaghica NL. : Bolkar Mountains translated from **Bolkar Dağları** in Turkish, and it is also known as Bulgar Dagh or Bolghar Dagh.

***Montivipera xanthina* (Gray, 1849)**

Xanthus,-ī m. Sg. L. :« **Xanthos** (Ξάνθος) m./f. Gr.: **Ksantos**, the ancient name of several rivers with "yellow water flowing", especially Eşen Stream in the Kınık town of Muğla on the border of Antalya and the ruins there [« **xanthós** (ξανθός): yellow] ****Montivipera xanthina***- Ottoman viper (snake) [type locality was restricted to "Xanthos (Muğla)"; similarly ***Barbus xanthos***, fish species described from the River Eşen].

***Vipera ammodytes* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

ammodytēs (hamm-),-ae m. L. :« **ammodytēs** (ἀμμοδύτης) Gr.: sand burrower, a kind of serpent in Africa [« **ámmos** (ἄμμος) f. Gr.: sand + **dýtēs** (δύτης) Gr.: diver].

***Vipera anatolica* Eiselt & Baran, 1970**

anatolicus,-a,-um L.: Anatolian [« **Anatolia,-ae** ML.: Anatolia, Asiatic Türkiye; « **anatolē** (ἀνατολή) Gr.: sunrise, place from where the sun rises, the east; « **anatéllō** (ἀνατέλλω): to rise; « **aná** (ἀνά): up + **téllō** (τέλλω): to perform, to rise), because Anatolia was east of Greece.

***Vipera berus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

berus :« **ber-slange** Old German: "(live) carrying snake" was Latinized as "*berus*" by Albertus Magnus [Ca. 1200-1280] (Uez et al., 2022), with meaning giving birth viper.

***Vipera darevskii* Vedmederja, Orlov & Tuniyev, 1986**

darevskii :« **Dr. Ilya Sergejevich Darevsky**, Russian herpetologist [q.v. ***Darevskia***]

***Vipera renardi* (Chirstoph, 1861)**

renardi :« **Dr. Charles Claude Renard** (originally **Karl Ivanovitch Renard**) [1809-1886], Russian naturalist and a Councillor of State. He became Secretary (before 1854) and President

(1884) of the Imperial Society of Naturalists in Moscow, where he was elected a member (1840). He was also elected as a member of the American Philosophical Society (1854). Hugo Theodor Christoph [1831-1894], the author of this snake, met with Renard (1860), who, as editor of the Moscow Society's Bulletin, published Christoph's paper (Beolens et al., 2011).

***Vipera sakoi* Tuniyev, Avci, Tuniyev, Ilgaz, Olgun, Petrova, Bodrov, Geniez & Teynié, 2018**
sakoi :« **Sako Tuniyev** [? –2015], studied vipers in the Caucasus and Northeast Anatolia and died tragically in 2015. *V. sakoi* was named in memory of Sako, son of the first author Boris, who formed the basis of this article.

***Vipera kaznakovi* Nikolsky, 1909**

kaznakovi :« **Aleksandr Nikolaevich Kaznakov** [1872-1933], Russian officer. Accompanied Pyotr K. Kozlov's expedition to Mongolia and Tibet to obtain a rich collection of the Imperial Russian Geographical Society (1899-1901), and many taxa were named after him. *Ptychobarbus kaznakovi* (fish) was also dedicated to him.

Family Elapidae Boie, 1827 (Cobras, Coral Snakes)

elap- :« **élaps** (ἔλαψ) Gr.: fish, serpent; « **éllops** (ἔλλοψ), genet. **éllapos** (ἔλλοπος) **m.** = **élops** (ἔλοψ) Gr.: fish in general [synonym: **ikhthýs** (ἰχθύς): European sea sturgeon (*Acipenser sturio*); a kind of snake] + **-idae pl.** L.: a suffix to form names of families of animals.

***Walterinnesia morgani* (Mocquard, 1905)**

Walterinnesia :« **Walter Francis Innes Bey** [1858–1937], physician and zoologist in Egypt.
morgani :« **M. de Morgan** [fl. 1905], (French) Iranian General Delegate at the Ministry of Education. Five specimens of the cobra, including the type specimen, and fossils, etc., collected during his mission in Iran. Mocquard gave his name to the new snake species in 1905, since he sent the collection containing 145 boxes to the museum.

Discussion

The binomial names of species frequently have been given by scientists to their external appearance, origin, or dedication to a certain person. A complete binomial name could be derived from a variety of sources Latin, Greek, other languages, names of people, and other sources such as anagrams, jokes, or puns (ICZN, 1999). The author indicated the origin of the binomial name of the Derivatio nominis part in the description article. Unfortunately, determining the etymology of many species' names is difficult, and it's especially a tedious process to go after old names.

A review of the material provides an assessment of both the diversity of all reptile species in Türkiye and the history of the region. The many taxonomists who name species and genera or have such taxa in their honor reflect a wide variety of people of many nationalities over more than two centuries of fieldwork in the country. In addition, the rich history of the country is reflected in the taxonomic records as place names. The names are still being given as new taxa are found, and these reflect the popular desire to name taxa for geographic places (e.g., *Vipera anatolica*, *Mediodactylus orientalis* and *Acanthodactylus harranensis*), for scientists who work on Turkish biodiversity (e.g. *Muhtarophis barani* and *Anatololacerta ibrahimi*), for the person first collecting the new species (e.g. *Walterinnesia morgani*), or as descriptions of habitats or morphological aspects of the taxa (e.g. *Lacerta viridis*).

Conclusion

According to the results, it has been determined that 37% of the species' names are based on the morphological characteristics of the species, 29% are based on honoring a person, and 22% are based on where they live. The other Latins originated from myth names/creatures, local names, anagrams, and habitat characteristics which contain 12% of them.

In conclusion, the Latin names of Türkiye's reptiles are mostly given in the characteristics and features of the species, in honor of a person or persons, or in geographic places. Reviewing the etymologies of the Latin names of reptile species living in Türkiye, compiling information and heritage will be very useful, especially for herpetologist.

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